

12th Annual Rising Voices Workshop

Co-creating Research, Policy, and Action: The Rising Voices of Indigenous Peoples and Partners in Weather and Climate Science

Monday, May 6 – Wednesday, May 8, 2024

Hybrid: In-person and Virtual

NSF National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR)

Center Green Campus, 3080 Center Green Drive

Boulder, CO

Website: <https://risingvoices.ucar.edu/>

In 2013, the first Rising Voices workshop at the National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR) asked: *What are the elements of successful co-production of science and policy in the related fields of extreme weather and climate change?* Over a decade later, engaging both Indigenous and Earth sciences to address climate change challenges is increasingly accepted and promoted within mainstream scientific enterprises. Funding agencies and institutions are increasingly requiring “meaningful community engagement” for research proposals and the “co-production of knowledge” is the term du jour in climate science research.

“The urgent threat posed by our climate crisis necessitates innovative actions. Innovation is an opportunity to look beyond Earth sciences to solutions in other knowledge systems and, in doing so, to support the rising voices of those who have been historically marginalized.”

– Lazrus et al., 2022

In this context, and building from the Rising Voices’ [Declaration on Relationships and the Wise Use and Applications of Technologies for Climate Actions for Everyone](#), we’re poised to learn from where we’ve been and grow into where we’re going. How can we work to better advance science, remove the boundaries between science and society, and create innovative partnerships among collaborators with diverse disciplinary and cultural backgrounds to support adaptive and resilient communities, and to achieve culturally relevant and scientifically robust climate and weather actions?

This workshop will bring participants together to work on proposed pathways and guidelines for intercultural collaborations for co-created, place-based Earth systems science research, policy, practice, and action. The focus will include the:

- Rising Voices' core priorities: (1) advancing science through collaborations that bring Indigenous and Earth sciences into partnership; (2) create opportunities for Indigenous students and early career scientists through scientific and community mentoring, and (3) support adaptive and resilient communities through sharing scientific capacity.
- Topics: Community relocation/site expansion; Education, Communication, Training, & Outreach; Energy Systems; Food Systems; Human Health; Phenology; and Water Systems.
- Regions: Pacific Coastal (Pacific Islands, Alaska, Northwest); Grass/shrub/arid lands (Southwest, Plains/North Central, South Central); Deciduous Forests (Midwest/Great lakes, Northeast); Atlantic Coastal (Gulf Coast, Southeast, Caribbean Islands, Northeast)

The Rising Voices Center serves as connective webbing, creating linkages and space for new collaborations to have their own life. This workshop focus is in direct response from requests by Rising Voices participants to initiate more regional and place-based work for a process of co-learning together.

The objective is to:

Develop general guidelines, principles, and evaluative processes that can be adapted for place-based intercultural collaborations in support of climate actions and the initiation of such collaborations in the relationship building phase.

As Rising Voices is working to pivot into a more place-based, actionable science initiative for intercultural climate collaborations, the goal of this convening is to build from long-standing engagement to collaboratively work together to move from a decade+ of Rising Voices' recommendations into action and commitment.

Day 1: Monday, May 6th

8:00am	<i>Orientation for 1st time RVers/students (optional)</i>
8:30am	<i>Coffee & Tea at NSF NCAR Center Green</i>
9:00am	Opening Ceremony - Steven LaPointe
9:20am	Welcome to Place - Ava Hamilton
9:30am	Welcome to the 12th Annual Rising Voices Workshop
9:50am	Welcome to NSF NCAR - Gretchen Mullendore
10:00am	Rising Voices video
10:15am	Setting the framework: Where we've been, where we're aiming to go
10:20am	Introductions
10:45am	<i>Break</i>
11:00am	Planting the seed: Connections, Opportunities, and Engagement Shantel Martinez (moderator), Paulette Blanchard, Diamond Tachera, Bill Thomas, Tyler Moore, Daniel Wildcat, Corinne Salter
12:10pm	Group dialogues
12:30pm	<i>Group photo (outside)</i>
12:40pm	<i>Lunch (mentoring relationships - grab food and connect together at tables outside)</i>

1:30pm	Examples of intercultural collaborations that center justice in climate research and action - inspiration for what's possible!
1:45pm	Building relationships and trust: Scientific collaboration responding to communities' needs - building air quality sensors in Lahaina Diamond Tachera (moderator), Keahi Tajon, Maraya Ben-Joseph, Agbeli Ameko, Keith Maull
2:35pm	<i>Transition to working groups – topic</i>
2:45pm	Working groups by topic Community relocation/site expansion Education, Communication, Training, & Outreach Energy Systems Food Systems Health Phenology Water Systems
4:00pm	<i>Break</i>
4:15pm	Share-out: initial reflections from Topics' groups Developing guidelines, principles, and evaluative processes that can be adapted for place-based intercultural collaborations in support of climate actions and collaborations in the relationship building phase
4:45pm	Wrap-up Day 1, What's coming up next Tribute to RV co-founders, Heather Lazrus and Bob Gough
5:00pm	Depart Center Green for Foothills Lab
5:15 - 7:30pm	The Annual Bob Gough-Fest "Climate Change is Inevitable, Adaptation is Optional" The Bob Gough Award for Climate Justice in Action Dinner

Day 2: Tuesday, May 7th

8:30am	<i>Coffee & Tea at NSF NCAR Center Green</i>
9:00am	Welcome to the day
9:10am	Recap Day 1 / Process Day 2
9:15am	Research, Policy, and Action: Scaling across governance systems Aranzazu Lascurain (moderator), Ramsay Taum, Chief Deme Naquin, Jainey Bavishi
10:15am	Group dialogues
10:35am	<i>Break & Transition to Working Groups - Topics</i>
11:00am	Working Groups by Topic (continued) Community relocation/site expansion Education, Communication, Training, & Outreach Energy Systems Food Systems Health Phenology Water Systems
12:15pm	<i>Lunch</i>
1:15pm	Storytelling & digital technology demonstration - Chris Shaeffer, Lomikai Media
1:30pm	World Café & Posters
2:30pm	<i>Transition to working groups – region</i>
2:40pm	Working groups by region Atlantic Coastal (Gulf Coast, Southeast, Caribbean Islands, Northeast) Deciduous Forests (Midwest/Great lakes, Northeast) Grass/shrub/arid lands (Southwest, Plains/North Central, South Central) Pacific Coastal (Pacific Islands, Alaska, Northwest)

4:00pm	<i>Break</i>
4:15pm	Share-out: initial reflections from Regional groups Developing guidelines, principles, and evaluative processes that can be adapted for place-based intercultural collaborations in support of climate actions and collaborations in the relationship building phase
4:45pm	Wrap-up Day 2, What's coming up next

Day 3: Wednesday, May 8th

8:30am	<i>Coffee & Tea at NSF NCAR Center Green</i>
9:00am	Welcome to the day
9:10am	Recap Day 2/Process Day 3 & Focused goal of today
9:15am	Localizing Rising Voices: Next steps, actions, and commitments <i>Share reflections from Topics & Regional Groups</i> – develop draft guidelines, principles, and evaluative processes that can be adapted for place-based intercultural collaborations in support of climate actions and collaborations in the relationship building phase
10:15am	<i>Break</i>
10:30am	Localizing Rising Voices: Next steps, actions, and commitments (continued)
11:15am	Growing Our Garden: Closing Reflections Annette Woolley, Cameran Bahnsen, Shelby Ross
11:45am	Closing Ceremony
<i>Please remember to complete and return your workshop evaluation survey!</i>	